

EFFICACY OF SKILL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS: AN ANALYSIS OF PRADHAN MANTRI KAUSHAL VIKAS YOJANA IN KARNATAKA STATE

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Research Guide

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Abstract

The Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana is an innovative programme designed to train the Indian youngsters and close the skills gaps that have emerged in the economy. To fulfil the goals of Skill India, the Hon. Prime Minister inaugurated this programme on 15th July 2015. India the nation with most youthful population craved to name itself as provider of talented youth to the worldwide prerequisites.

This scheme was carried out in three phases.i.e, PMKVY, PMKVY 2.0, and PMKVY 3.0 from 2015 to 2022. The performance of this scheme is very promising. With the available literature and information gathered from the Right to information act, this paper will make an attempt to analyze the performance of this Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana in Karnataka state. The evaluation of this Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana will reveal the training programs effectiveness and helps in understanding the challenges and problems faced by the Training centres, Trainees and the entire ecosystem of this program.

Keywords: PMKVY, Skills, Skill development, Trained, Assessed, Certified and Placed

Introduction: Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana is ambitious skill development training scheme launched by Government of India in 2015. With its unique characteristics like Allowance to Trainees, Training conducted against standards (National Occupational Standards - NOS and Qualification Packs - QPs for specific job roles) formulated by industry-driven bodies, namely the Sector Skills Councils (SSCs), recognition for prior learning and mentorship has created lot of expectations from both industry and trainees. As the scheme is targeted to align with the demand from the Central Governments flagship programmes, such as - Swachh Bharat, Make in India, Digital India, National Solar Mission and so on, this scheme may bring some revolutionary reforms in Skill Development and Employment aspects.

This Scheme was lunched to instill the desired skills among Indian youth. In these 7 years of journey (2015-2022) PMKVY scheme has reached the whole country. Already 3 phases of PMKVY are over and now PMKVY 4.0 will come into force from 2022 to till 2026. Based upon the national skills qualifications frame work (NSQF) 31 sector skill councils were recognized for PMKVY. In these sectors youth were trained, certified and placed. Recognition of prior learning is the added advantage

for those who undergone training in past. This training program can be viewed as integrated approach to strengthen existing capabilities and caliber of the Indian youth.

Research objectives

1. To Study the structure and implementation of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana
2. To analyze the effectiveness of PMKVY 2.0 & PMKVY 3.0

Research Methodology

Research Method: Exploratory Research design is adopted for this study.

Secondary data sources: data provided by Government departments, Research Articles, Internet, Newspaper Articles and Journals etc.

Analysis and Interpretation: Secondary data is processed and conclusions are drawn.

Need for the study: post independence India has lunched series of skill development schemes designed and executed by government and private agencies, but India is comparatively lagging in creating skilled workers as per the industry and job market requirements. Though the up gradation in designing the skill development programs has done, the success rate of these programs are not met the expected level. There is a need of reviewing of these schemes.

Scope for the study: This kind of studies will provide the insights and background of the PMKVY. The study may be helpful in identifying the shortfalls and probable obstacles in executing this training program.

Limitations of the Study:

- 1) Only the state of Karnataka is included in the study..
- 2) The Study is confined to review PMKVY scheme.

Literature Review :

Awareness, Perception and Youth mobilization towards PMKVY training in Haryana by Ashwani Kumar Joshi and K. N. Pandey, International Journal of Management (IJM) Volume 11, Issue 11, November 2020, pp. 2528-2537. Article ID: IJM_11_11_237: This paper highlighted about the significance of the skills for employment and further major skill development initiatives of Government and budget allocation as well as statistics of candidates trained, placed and assessed were discussed. the paper with objectives of examining the youth mobilization and awareness of PMKVY through Kaushala Mela, then correlation between PMKVY components and youth satisfaction focused on PMKVY programs were elaborated. finally paper is concluded as in Haryana the awareness level of PMKVY among youth is very high and Kaushal Mela were successful, as the participation of youths in this Mela were spreading the positive mouth of words about PMKVY, which resulted in effective

awareness about this program. But there is partial satisfaction of youth towards PMKVY was found but still there is a lot of Expectations from this program exist.

Skill Development Initiatives in India: An Exploratory Study with Special Reference to Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana by Dr. Ajay Solkhe, Dipika,IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM) e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 23, Issue 2. Ser. IV (February 2021), PP 07-14 www.iosrjournals.org : This paper aimed at investigating the structural framework of skill development programmes in India. more than 40 schemes are framed to increase the employability skills of youth. further the progress of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana was reviewed and commented on its performance. an ambitious skill development program named PMKVY was launched by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on 15th July 2015 to supply the skilled human resources to 24 key sectors of the Indian economy. as only 2.3 % of its total workforce undergone formal training, PMKVY was planned to train 109 million people by 2022 in India. the paper focuses on the framework of PMKVY and evaluation of PMKVY progress. The study also focused on problems and difficulties encountered during the execution of PMKVY. The paper concluded saying that, affiliation process of PMKVY scheme is Lengthy and exhausting. problems in training of trainers, mobilization of youths, placement challenges are the obstacles faced by PMKVY. Lastly the challenge of achieving the target of training 1 crore people is still under process. placements and awareness about PMKVY or not satisfactory during the tenure 2016 to 2020.

Study of the profile of the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 2.0 in India an overview by Dr. Shanta Arakeri V. and Satish Sonawane International Journal of Advance and Applied Research (IJAAR) Impact Factor –7.328, ISSN – 2347-7075 Peer Reviewed Bi-Monthly Vol.8 No.5 May – June 2021: this article encompasses on describing and analyzing The detailed profile of PMKVY in India with its key components and further paper has thrown light on understanding the fundamental framework of PMKVY. the article used secondary data and Analysis of PMKVY 1.0,PMKVY 2.0 and PMKVY 3.0. Finally concluded that, PMKVY has contributed in enhancing employability skills and generated employments, This PMKVY programme has made it possible for young people to enrol in industry-relevant skill training, which guarantees better livelihood.

Evaluating the perception of PMKVY beneficiaries Sanchay Bapat, Akansha Pandey International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management (IJSREM) Volume: 03 Issue: 11 | Nov -2019 : this paper is based upon the survey conducted on PMKVY beneficiaries with the research objectives, to understand the various opportunities and challenges related to training. the paper also tried to understand the perception of beneficiaries of PMKVY in Mysore and Chamarajanagar districts of Karnataka. the analysis is being done using the hypothesis and Chi square test, the inferences of the study were the PMKVY scheme has positively influenced the beneficiaea and they were recommending this training to others also. Whereas on the other side the scheme is suffering from some lacunae, such as lack of awareness about the various components of PMKVY scheme, less entrepreneurship opportunities available.

Impact of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana on the Productivity of Youth in Gwalior Region, India by mini agra, International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE): this paper made an effort to assess the impact of the PMKVY in improving the productivity of youths in Gwalior region. the paper concluded that in Gwalior region the PMKVY scheme

improved the productivity of the youths while performing the jobs. till there is a need of changes in the framework of PMKVY.

To study the impact of the covid – 19 pandemic on the PMKVY on the students of the central India by Ms. Shikha Singh and Ms. Shinki Katyayani Pandey, International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECS) ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 03 2022 : this paper attempts to analyse the effectiveness of PMKVY in Chhattisgarh and to study the impact of pandemic on PMKVY, as this paper is based on conceptual study and secondary data. the paper ended stating that, as the pmkvy scheme is struggling to get the desired number of trainees, due to lack of awareness the beneficiaries are also not getting the employment after completing the training, covid-19 has badly affected this scheme.

Perception of Training partners towards skill development and training outcome at implementation stage of PMKVY program : an empirical study by Dr.K.P.Balakrishnan, Dr.K.Senthilkumar, The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, Volume XII, Issue X, October/2020,ISSN NO:0886-9367 : this paper discussed the shortcomings and prospects of training partners at the implementation stage of PMKVY program. observations of the paper are, still there is a need of improvement in training facilities to achieve the better training outcomes. the paper suggested that government has to upgrade the existing training centres and contemporary curriculum that exist in international Arena should be adopted for training the youths. Finally the conclusion was to concentrate more on quality rather than quantity.

Facts and Figures about Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Karnataka

1. Financial Year wise candidates trained under PMKVY 2.0 and 3.0 in Karnataka (as on 31. 12.2021)

Financial Year	Enrolled	Ongoing	Trained	Assessed	Certified	Reported Placed
2016-17	17,980	0	9,713	784	550	104
2017-18	83,716	0	70,487	63,025	63,025	5,817
2018-19	1,10,922	0	1,10,111	89,987	89,987	22,299
2019-20	2,17,053	0	1,65,247	1,47,281	1,47,281	20,845

(Source: Right to Information Act (RTI) under RTI 2005)

2. Number of Training Centers in Karnataka under PMKVY 2.0 and 3.0 Schemes as on 31. 12.2021

Scheme	Total training Centers (TC's)
PMKVY 2.0	278
PMKVY 3.0	104
Grand Total	382

(Source: Right to Information Act (RTI) under RTI 2005)

3. Gender wise Candidates Enrolled, Undergoing training, Trained, Assessed, Certified and Placed from 2016 to 2021 in Karnataka (All Schemes of PMKVY)

Gender	Scheme	Enrolled	Ongoing	Trained / Oriented	Assessed	Certified	Reported Placed

Female	PMKVY 2.0	157968	0	146840	132407	124466	29934
Female	PMKVY 3.0	3177	0	3150	2471	1588	357
Male	PMKVY 2.0	257429	0	242504	213189	197505	27624
Male	PMKVY 3.0	11312	60	11179	6114	3238	304
Transgender	PMKVY 2.0	3	0	2	1	0	0

(Source: Right to Information Act (RTI) under RTI 2005)

4. Sector Skills Council wise Candidates Enrolled, Undergoing training, Trained, Assessed, Certified and Placed from 2016 to 2021 in Karnataka (All Schemes of PMKVY)

Scheme	Sector	Enrolled	Ongoing	Trained / Oriented	Assessed	Certified	Reported placed
PMKVY 2.0	Aerospace and Aviation	2517	0	2514	1912	1911	0
PMKVY 2.0	Agriculture	19350	0	19131	17199	15766	206
PMKVY 2.0	Apparel	75164	0	72300	62622	61435	13079
PMKVY 2.0	Automotive	10019	0	10019	9647	8592	152
PMKVY 2.0	Beauty and Wellness	10630	0	10394	8919	8365	733
PMKVY 2.0	BFSI	6821	0	6786	6350	4904	2121
PMKVY 2.0	Capital Goods	2334	0	2136	1963	1651	745
PMKVY 2.0	Construction	17182	0	16377	13341	11792	1669
PMKVY 2.0	Domestic Workers	3367	0	3344	3228	3223	0
PMKVY 2.0	Electronics and Hardware	44964	0	39010	36743	32831	14673
PMKVY 2.0	Food Processing	1068	0	1033	864	854	42
PMKVY 2.0	Furniture and Fittings	1126	0	1126	885	877	0
PMKVY 2.0	Gems and Jewellery	12466	0	12459	11007	10613	145

PMKVY 2.0	Green Jobs	1535	0	1403	1368	1330	586
PMKVY 2.0	Handicrafts and Carpet	1731	0	1731	1634	1633	32
PMKVY 2.0	Healthcare	883	0	729	652	615	236
PMKVY 2.0	Hydrocarbon	13883	0	11927	9185	8994	0
PMKVY 2.0	Infrastructure Equipment	2854	0	2853	2728	2727	4
PMKVY 2.0	Iron and Steel	8315	0	8103	7252	7120	1386
PMKVY 2.0	IT-ITeS	27401	0	21851	19943	16508	6791
PMKVY 2.0	Leather	1110	0	1110	1039	1014	131
PMKVY 2.0	Life Sciences	8186	0	8185	7907	6657	0
PMKVY 2.0	Logistics	25288	0	24537	21752	20861	4592
PMKVY 2.0	Management	40802	0	40612	33081	31351	71
PMKVY 2.0	Media and Entertainment	5373	0	5122	5107	5051	417
PMKVY 2.0	Mining	950	0	944	928	809	529
PMKVY 2.0	Paints And Coatings	263	0	263	187	166	0
PMKVY 2.0	Persons with Disability	300	0	300	59	0	0
PMKVY 2.0	Plumbing	4345	0	3938	3252	2792	486
PMKVY 2.0	Power	173	0	126	117	102	5
PMKVY 2.0	Retail	19389	0	17062	15924	14396	4791
PMKVY 2.0	Rubber	5664	0	5188	4502	4211	0
PMKVY 2.0	Security	3509	0	3417	3160	2783	744
PMKVY 2.0	Sports	1681	0	1681	1642	1589	251

PMKVY 2.0	Telecom	3354	0	3071	2887	2528	1086
PMKVY 2.0	Textiles And Handlooms	15138	0	15124	14454	14412	0
PMKVY 2.0	Tourism & Hospitality	16265	0	13440	12157	11508	1855
PMKVY 3.0	Aerospace and Aviation	1828	0	1828	568	19	0
PMKVY 3.0	Agriculture	34	0	34	0	0	0
PMKVY 3.0	Apparel	605	0	605	381	281	66
PMKVY 3.0	Automotive	496	0	496	422	397	0
PMKVY 3.0	Beauty and Wellness	294	0	293	176	59	0
PMKVY 3.0	Capital Goods	90	0	90	90	54	28
PMKVY 3.0	Construction	228	0	227	215	212	44
PMKVY 3.0	Electronics and Hardware	1405	0	1405	1247	894	190
PMKVY 3.0	Furniture and Fittings	164	0	164	164	164	0
PMKVY 3.0	Gems and Jewellery	988	0	988	960	0	0
PMKVY 3.0	Green Jobs	60	0	60	46	20	0
PMKVY 3.0	Healthcare	607	0	591	457	74	0
PMKVY 3.0	Hydrocarbon	12	0	12	0	0	0
PMKVY 3.0	Infrastructure Equipment	426	0	426	426	346	0
PMKVY 3.0	Iron and Steel	1266	0	1266	343	112	15
PMKVY 3.0	IT-ITeS	1620	60	1514	1022	839	152
PMKVY 3.0	Leather	597	0	596	399	0	0
PMKVY 3.0	Life Sciences	112	0	112	34	16	0

PMKVY 3.0	Logistics	1104	0	1069	253	194	9
PMKVY 3.0	Management	708	0	708	416	387	0
PMKVY 3.0	Media and Entertainment	55	0	55	54	30	0
PMKVY 3.0	Plumbing	90	0	90	77	72	0
PMKVY 3.0	Retail	698	0	698	439	300	89
PMKVY 3.0	Rubber	52	0	52	38	38	0
PMKVY 3.0	Telecom	120	0	120	108	87	15
PMKVY 3.0	Tourism & Hospitality	830	0	830	250	231	53

(Source: Right to Information Act (RTI) under RTI 2005)

Discussions:

Observations from the existing literature are pretty evident that Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana is a unique and updated skill development program. This is designed to upgrade the current skill sets of Indian youth. In some cases the awareness about PMKVY is quite satisfactory, whereas in some part of the country the awareness level is still in infancy stage. Kaushal meals are playing a vital role in reaching the rural areas.

The challenge in implementing PMKVY is mobilization of youth. The training centres are facing problems in getting desired numbers of trainees, due to its complicated affiliation process, as the process is lengthy and exhaustive. Especially during 2019-20 and 2020-21, due to the covid-19 pandemic offline training classes were impossible to run and placing the certified beneficiaries became difficult.

The scheme is doing well in Haryana and Gwalior, where the trainees and beneficiaries were spreading positive mouth of words, this scheme improved the productivity of youths and it reflected in their job performance.

In 2016-17, out of 17,980 enrolled, only 9713 were completed their training and 550 trainees were certified and 104 trainees were placed, it shows that 57 % of total enrolled were trained and only 3.6 % trainees got certify. Only 0.77% trainees were placed. Overall performance was poor.

In 2017-18, out of 83,716 enrolled, 70,487 were completed their training and 63,025 trainees were certified and 5,817 trainees were placed. It can be analyzed as 87 % of total enrolled were trained and

around 77 % were reported placed. Overall performance was outstanding and effectiveness of the program was at its best during this tenure.

In 2018-19, out of 1,10,922 enrolled, 1,10,111 were trained and 89,987 were certified. 22,299 trainees reported placed, the numbers says that, 97% of total enrolled were trained, 67% of total enrolled were certified and 26 % reported placed. Though the rate of placement came down, the percentage of trained was good.

In 2019-20, out of 2,17,053 enrolled, 1,65,247 were trained, around 1,47,281 were certified and 20,845 trainees reported placed. These numbers were talking about. Out of total enrolled 70% of them were trained and 67% trainees were successfully certified. The rate of placement was 9.6% training scheme was successful in maintaining its consistency with previous years performance.

Total enrollment of male candidates during PMKVY 2.0 and PMKVY 3.0 were 2,68,741 out of these total enrollment, 2,53,683 were completed training successfully. From the total enrollment 2,00,743 were certified. Lastly 27,928 were placed. The percentages of trained, certified and placed were 97%, 78 % and 10 % respectively. Performance in placement was not satisfactory.

Total enrollment of female candidates during PMKVY 2.0 and PMKVY 3.0 were 1,61,145 out of this total enrollment 1,49,990 were completed training successfully. From the total enrollment 1,26,054 were certified. Lastly the total of 30,291 were placed. the percentage of trained and certified and placed were 97% ,70% and 10 % respectively. The rate of placement was not good.

During PMKVY 2.0, 31 sector skill council were identified by NSDC. Apparel sector attracted more number of training aspirants and got enrollment about 75,164 out of this total trainees 72,300 were trained and 61435 were certified with 13,079 placements. Percentage of trained, certified and placed were 96% , 81 % and 17 % respectively.

The second highest enrolled sector was Electronics and Hardware and total enrollment was 44,984 and 39,010 were trained, out of this total enrolled 32831 trainees were certified and 14,613 were successfully placed. Percentage of trained, certified and placed were 80%, 77 % and 32 % respectively.

The third maximum enrollment were in management sector with 40,802, of this total enrollment 40,612 were trained and 31,351 were certified, the number of trainees placed successfully were around 71, the trainees certified, placed and placed were 98%, 70% and 0.17 % respectively.

The least enrolled sector during PMKVY 2.0 was hydrocarbon sector, with just 12 enrollment and out of this total enrollment all 12 were trained but nobody got certified and reported placed, which was the worst performance observed.

Conclusion:

The paper can be concluded that the third largest economy in the world needs more skilled and trained human resources as inflow to achieve the five trillion economy and making India as International hub

for skilled youths. Due to Covid-19, during 2019-20 and 2020-21 PMKVY scheme was badly affected. As the NSDC recently notified PMKVY 4.0 for 2022 to 2026, shortfalls and challenges of the PMKVY can be anticipated by considering the present situation.. Government can achieve its target of skilling 1 Crore people across the country by reviewing and revising the components of PMKVY (the past researches pointed out that, issues pertaining to affiliation and training facilities of PMKVY should be fixed) in Karnataka.

In Karnataka, total enrolled, certified and placed were not satisfactory, the revival of economy is possible by its all 24 identified sectors with their outstanding performance. But the figures collected on sector skill Council wise enrollment, certified and placed were highly concentrated on Apparel, Electronics and Hardware and Management. The remaining sectors can be made effective by creating more awareness and proper placement assistance.

References:

1. Awareness, Perception and Youth mobilization towards PMKVY training in Haryana by Ashwani Kumar Joshi and K. N. Pandey, International Journal of Management (IJM) Volume 11, Issue 11, November 2020, pp. 2528-2537. Article ID: IJM_11_11_237
2. Skill Development Initiatives in India: An Exploratory Study with Special Reference to Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana by Dr. Ajay Solkhe, Dipika, IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM) e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 23, Issue 2. Ser. IV (February 2021), PP 07-14 www.iosrjournals.org
3. Study of the profile of the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 2.0 in India an overview by Dr. Shanta Arakeri V. and Satish Sonawane International Journal of Advance and Applied Research (IJAAR) Impact Factor –7.328, ISSN – 2347-7075 Peer Reviewed Bi-Monthly Vol.8 No.5 May – June 2021
4. Evaluating the perception of PMKVY beneficiaries Sanchay Bapat, Akansha Pandey International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management (IJSREM) Volume: 03 Issue: 11 | Nov -2019
5. Impact of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana on the Productivity of Youth in Gwalior Region, India by mini agra, International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)
6. To study the impact of the covid – 19 pandemic on the PMKVY on the students of the central India by Ms. Shikha Singh and Ms. Shinki Katyayani Pandey, International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECS) ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 03 2022
7. Perception of Training partners towards skill development and training outcome at implementation stage of PMKVY program : an empirical study by Dr.K.P.Balakrishnan, Dr.K.Senthilkumar, The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, Volume XII, Issue X, October/2020, ISSN NO:0886-9367
8. <http://www.pmkvyofficial.org>
9. <https://nsdcindia.org>
10. <https://eskillindia.org>